

The Use of Digital Finance for Inclusive Growth in India- Scope and Challenges.

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Abstract.

Financial services are very crucial for any economy, as they empower both households and businesses to save, invest, and safeguard themselves against risks. Financial institutions and governments also face losses due to the widespread use of cash. In emerging economies, 93 per cent of all transactions are conducted in cash, compared to 50 per cent in developed economies. Policy initiatives such as the 2016 demonetization and the introduction of the goods and services tax have played a role in fostering the adoption of digital financial systems. Moreover, the COVID-19 pandemic has expedited the acceptance of digital financial services across various socioeconomic sectors. The paper based on secondary data found that technological infrastructure, financial literacy, Economic social and cultural factors, Govt initiatives play significant role in the use of digital finance in our country. The study also found that enhanced digital and financial literacy programmes, rural outreach programmes, simplification of the onboarding process and strong regulatory support are essential for enhancing the use of digital finance and financial inclusion in our country.

Key words: digital finance, financial inclusion, financial literacy, demonetisation, Covid19

Introduction

Financial services are crucial for any economy, as they empower both households and businesses to save, invest, and safeguard themselves against risks. However, in many developing economies today, a significant portion of individuals and small businesses lack access to even basic financial products like savings accounts and credit. This limitation not only hampers economic growth but also perpetuates poverty. Addressing this issue involves overcoming barriers such as inadequate infrastructure, low financial literacy, and regulatory challenges. Technological advancements, especially in fintech, can play a pivotal role in bridging this gap. Additionally, government and regulatory efforts are essential to promote financial inclusion, creating a more inclusive financial system that benefits a larger segment of the population. The ultimate aim is to foster sustainable economic development and reduce poverty by ensuring broader access to financial services.

A robust financial service sector is crucial for a nation's economic well-being, facilitating savings, insurance against anticipated and unforeseen events, and supporting investments in new ventures. It empowers individuals and businesses to efficiently manage transactions and supply chains. Unfortunately, those in emerging economies face limited access to financial services compared to their counterparts in advanced economies. Nearly 45% of the adult population in developing nations, equivalent to two billion people, lacks accounts with banks, financial institutions, or mobile money services. Furthermore, 200 million micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs), comprising half of such businesses in emerging economies, struggle to secure sufficient credit for their growth. Financial institutions and governments also face losses due to the widespread use of cash. In emerging economies, 93 per cent of all

transactions are conducted in cash, compared to 50 per cent in developed economies. This high reliance on cash increases costs for service providers and discourages them from catering to millions of less affluent customers and smaller businesses. For instance, in Ethiopia, India, Nigeria, and Pakistan, over 99 per cent of transactions by volume are in cash, covering everything from real estate deals to vehicle registrations. Similarly, 94 per cent of all transactions in China still involve cash. Cash-based payment systems pose challenges for governments, leading to inefficient expenditure and tax collection processes. In some instances, as much as one-third of such payments may be lost to corruption. (Mckinsey, 2016)

Objective of Study

Two billion individuals and 200 million businesses in emerging economies today lack access to savings and credit, and even those with access can pay dearly for a limited range of products. Rapidly spreading digital technologies now offer an opportunity to provide financial services at much lower cost, and therefore boosting financial inclusion and enabling large productivity gains across the economy. The benefits of digital financial services delivered via mobile phones, the internet or cards are many. The main objectives of the paper include

1. To study the development of digital financial services in India.
2. To study the factors influencing digital finance and its challenges in India
3. To suggest measures to overcome difficulties in digital finance.

Research Methodology

The current study is exploratory in nature, relying on secondary data sources such as national and international journals, magazines, papers, and studies issued by research groups like as Deloitte, KPMG, Forbes, and Mckinsey etc. For the purpose

of the study, reports issued by various regulatory bodies such as the Reserve Bank of India (RBI), the National Payments Corporation of India (NPCI) etc. were also taken into account.

Analysis of Research Objectives

I To study the development of digital financial services in India.

Digital financial inclusion refers to internet access to the use of formal financial services by excluded and underserved populations. E-banking activity in rural India results in increased usage of financial services and improved living conditions due to technological involvement in financial inclusion. Financial inclusion, as a result of digital financial services, also promotes economic growth. Digital financial inclusion entails providing affordable digital access to formal banking services for individuals who have historically been excluded or underserved in the financial system.

Despite the Indian government's implementation of legislative measures to extend financial services to remote areas, achieving financial inclusion for the average person remains a persistent challenge. Policy initiatives such as the 2016 demonetization and the introduction of the goods and services tax have played a role in fostering the adoption of digital financial systems. Moreover, the COVID-19 pandemic has expedited the acceptance of digital financial services across various socioeconomic sectors. However, ongoing challenges, including barriers to access, lack of awareness, and the necessity for additional policy interventions, contribute to the complexity of achieving widespread financial inclusion. Mobile technology has made its way into every facet of professional and personal interactions. Mobile devices aren't just for communication; they're also an important part of the growing business paradigm (Aggarwal 2019). Over 80 nations have now adopted digital financial services, with a few reaching significant scale.

As an outcome, millions of previously ignored and underprivileged users are shifting away from money transactions Aggarwal, D. (2019). All the formal financial services such as payments, fund transfers, savings, credit, health coverage and even securities of which are accessible via mobile phone or other digital media. The image is rapidly evolving due to the development of ever more advanced technology. Apart from business correspondents (BC), payment banks, and small financing banks, digital financial inclusion has gained significance. Payments have been revolutionized due to innovations like IMPS, UPI, and AEPS. According to reports, 280 crore worth of transactions were done over UPI alone in June 2021 in India, reflecting the uptick in digital payment acceptance across socioeconomic groups throughout the month. Travel and physical involvement provide

opportunities for exposure. The more a rural person interacts with individuals in more urban surroundings outside of their block or tehsil, the more inclined they become to accept digital payments. This might simply be due to increased engagement with digital environments.

The aspirational association with "Digital India" (or "Digital Bharat") increased adoption, particularly among younger individuals. For some aspirational people, digital payments seem to be a replacement for an optimistic, technologically advanced vision of India, even in rural areas with little internet connectivity. More than any particular purpose, the desire to be more integrated into the digital economy drives the adoption of digital payments. Similar to big cities, ease was frequently cited as a reason for adopting digital payment methods. Compared to their urban counterparts, rural businesses stand to earn more from participating in a local digital economy because they incur higher costs for storing currency, such as lost revenue due to travel time to and from banks. (Nihanshi Goyal, 2022)

ii To study the factors influencing digital finance and its challenges in India

Digital financial services (DFS) encompass a wide range of financial services delivered through digital channels, such as mobile phones, the internet, and other electronic platforms. Various factors influence the adoption, growth, and success of digital financial services. Here are some key factors which influence digital finance and its challenges are

- **Technological Infrastructure.** The availability and reliability of digital networks, including mobile and the internet, play a crucial role. Areas with better network coverage are more likely to see widespread adoption of digital financial services. The penetration of digital devices, such as smartphones and tablets, is a significant factor. The affordability and accessibility of these devices can impact the ability of individuals to access digital financial services.
- **Regulatory Environment:** The regulatory environment significantly influences the development of digital financial services. Clear and supportive regulations can foster innovation and competition, while overly restrictive or ambiguous regulations may hinder growth. Effective regulations for consumer protection build trust in digital financial services. Regulations that address issues like fraud, data security, and privacy are crucial for user confidence.
- **Financial Literacy and Education:** The lack of awareness about digital financial services can be a barrier to adoption. Education campaigns and training programs can help build awareness and

understanding of the benefits and usage of these services. Financial Literacy: Understanding basic financial concepts and digital literacy is essential for users to navigate digital financial platforms effectively.

- Cultural and Social Factors: Cultural attitudes toward formal financial systems, trust in technology, and established financial behaviors can impact the adoption of digital financial services. Peer influence and social norms can affect individual decisions to adopt and use digital financial services.
- Economic Factors: The level of income in a population can affect the affordability of digital services. Lower-income populations may be more price-sensitive and may require more affordable and inclusive services. The availability and accessibility of traditional banking services can influence the adoption of digital financial services. In areas with limited access to traditional banks, digital services may be more attractive.
- Infrastructure and Interoperability: The availability of digital payment infrastructure, such as point-of-sale terminals and online payment gateways, can impact the usability of digital financial services.
- Market Competition: Healthy competition among digital financial service providers can lead to better services, innovation, and lower costs, making it more attractive for users.
- Security and Data Privacy: Robust security features and measures to protect against fraud and unauthorized access are critical for user trust. Clear policies and practices regarding the collection and use of user data are essential to address concerns about privacy.
- Government Initiatives: Supportive government policies and initiatives, such as financial inclusion programs, can drive the adoption of digital financial services. The presence of reliable digital identity systems can simplify onboarding processes and enhance the security of digital transactions.
- Global Trends and Technological Advancements: Advances in technology, such as the development of new payment methods, blockchain, and artificial intelligence, can shape the landscape of digital financial services. International Collaboration and alignment with global standards and initiatives can facilitate cross-border transactions and interoperability.

The interplay of these factors varies across different regions and communities, making it essential for stakeholders, including governments, financial institutions, and service providers, to consider local contexts when promoting and implementing digital financial services.

iii Suggestions for Improvement of Digital Finance in India.

Improving the use of digital finance in India involves addressing various aspects of infrastructure, regulation, education, and accessibility. Here are some suggestions:

- Digital Literacy Programs: - Implement widespread digital literacy programs to educate individuals about digital financial services, including online banking, mobile wallets, and digital payment platforms.
- Rural Outreach Programmes : Focus on extending digital financial services to rural areas by enhancing network infrastructure and promoting the use of smartphones. This could involve partnerships with private companies to build the necessary infrastructure.
- Simplified Onboarding Processes: Streamline the onboarding process for digital financial services by simplifying documentation requirements and making the process more user-friendly. This will encourage more people, especially those in rural areas, to adopt digital finance.
- Regulatory Support: Create a conducive regulatory environment that supports innovation in the digital finance sector while ensuring consumer protection. Clear regulations can attract more players and boost competition, leading to better services.
- Interoperability: -Promote interoperability among different digital payment systems to enable seamless transactions between various platforms. This can enhance user convenience and encourage the adoption of digital payment methods.
- Incentivize Digital Transactions : Introduce incentives for individuals and businesses to conduct transactions digitally. This could include cashback offers, discounts, or other rewards for using digital payment methods.
- Cybersecurity Measures Strengthen cybersecurity measures to build trust among users. Public awareness campaigns about cybersecurity best practices can also help in this regard.
- Integration with Social Programs: Integrate digital financial services with social welfare programs to disburse benefits directly to beneficiaries' digital accounts. This can reduce leakages, and fraud, and improve efficiency.
- Collaboration with Fintech Startups: Encourage collaboration between traditional financial institutions and fintech startups to bring innovative solutions to the market. This can lead to the development of new, user-friendly financial products.

- **Enhanced Customer Support:** Improve customer support for digital financial services to address concerns and issues promptly. This can enhance trust and confidence in digital finance platforms.
- **Promotion of UPI (Unified Payments Interface):** Continue promoting and improving UPI, a real-time payment system developed by the National Payments Corporation of India. UPI has played a significant role in boosting digital transactions in the country.
- **Financial Inclusion Initiatives:** - Continue and expand financial inclusion initiatives to bring more people into the formal financial system. This includes efforts to provide banking services to those who are currently underserved or excluded.

Implementing these suggestions collectively can contribute to the widespread adoption and effective use of digital finance in India.

Conclusion:

The future of digital finance in India is poised for continued growth, driven by the rise of innovative fintech solutions and expanding digital infrastructure. Government initiatives, such as Digital India, are fostering financial inclusion, especially in rural areas. The adoption of technologies like UPI, mobile wallets, and blockchain is reshaping the payments landscape. Traditional banks are increasingly embracing digital transformation, aiming to provide seamless online banking experiences. Cybersecurity will remain a paramount concern as the sector evolves, necessitating robust measures to ensure the security of digital transactions.

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